
DEMONSTRATION OF THE EQUIVALENCE BETWEEN TWO DISTRICT HEATING NETWORKS OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a demonstration of the equivalence between the optimization problem minimizing the supply cost of $p \in \mathbb{N}$ independent District Heating Networks (DHN) and the optimization problem minimizing the supply cost of a single aggregated DHN. This demonstration is presented in three stages. First, we demonstrate the equivalence in the case of two DHNs, each one composed of two plants. In the second stage, we enlarge the demonstration for two DHNs with n plants. Finally, the general demonstration (p DHNs and n plants) is presented. Although the last demonstration includes the previous cases, the two first sections are necessary to understand the general demonstration.

1 Demonstration: equivalence of aggregation problems

Figure 1: Aggregation of two simple DHNs into an aggregated one

1.1 Description of the optimization problems and notations

Suppose we have $p = 2$ independent District Heating Networks (DHN).

Each DHN is composed of two plants $G_{i,1}$ and $G_{i,2}$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$ is the DHN index. $G_{i,1}$ is the base plant with a marginal cost inferior to $G_{i,2}$. All these plants can produce such as: $0 \leq P_{G_{i,j}}(t) \leq \overline{P_{G_{i,j}}}(t) \leq P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$. These DHNs are sized to meet their local demand $load_i$, meaning that $\forall t, P_{G_{i,1}}^{max} + P_{G_{i,2}}^{max} \leq load_i(t)$. The notation $\overline{P}(t)$ allows to ceil the produced power depending on time, whereas P^{max} is the plant's maximum power for all time.

For the aggregated case, we use the same technologies with a sizing corresponding to the sum of the two sizings: G_1 is the same technology as $G_{1,1}$ and $G_{2,1}$, and $P_{G_1}^{max} = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$. These plants G_1 and G_2 answer the load curve $\forall t, load(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t)$.

The demonstrations are given for all t under the condition of a constant merit order. If the merit order changes over time, it is sufficient to add the same constraint for each possible merit order, see Section 1.5 for a detailed justification. Multiplying these constraints does not affect the results as the constraints are intrinsically inactive when the merit order does not correspond. Also regarding merit order, it is supposed that plants with the same indexes have the same marginal cost, meaning that for all $j \in \mathbb{N}$, producing with $P_{G_{1,j}}$ is equivalent to producing with $P_{G_{2,j}}$.

1.2 Full optimization problem

For each DHN i ($i \in \{1, 2\}$) in front of the load curve $load_i$, we have the following optimization problem:

$$\min (cost_{G_{i,1}} + cost_{G_{i,2}}) \quad (\text{OBJ-}i)$$

subject to the load balancing:

$$P_{G_{i,1}}(t) + P_{G_{i,2}}(t) = load_i(t) \quad (\text{LB-}i)$$

The merit order in the DHN i , $G_{i,1}$ producing before $G_{i,2}$, can be expressed as such:

$$P_{G_{i,2}}(t) \leq \max (load_i(t) - \overline{P_{G_{i,1}}}(t); 0) \quad (\text{MO-}i)$$

Therefore, the full optimization problem features two independent optimization problems for DHNs 1 and 2.

1.3 Simplified optimization problem

The aggregated optimization problem is:

$$\min (cost_{G_1} + cost_{G_2}) \quad (\text{OBJ})$$

subject to:

$$P_{G_1}(t) + P_{G_2}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t) \quad (\text{LB})$$

and:

$$P_{G_2}(t) \leq \max(load(t) - \overline{P_{G_1}}(t); 0) \quad (\text{MO})$$

We add a new constraint to restrain the base plant production according to local demands:

$$\overline{P_{G_1}}(t) = \min(P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}; load_1(t)) + \min(P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}; load_2(t)) \quad (\text{AGG})$$

1.4 Equivalence of optimization problems

Let us show that these two optimization problems are equivalent, i.e. that their solutions are the same. Case disjunction.

If $load_1(t) \leq P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \leq P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$:

(MO-1) becomes $P_{G_{1,2}}(t) = 0$. Same for (MO-2).

Using (LB-1) and (LB-2), the solutions to the full optimization problem are:

- $P_{G_{1,1}}(t) = load_1(t)$ and $P_{G_{1,2}}(t) = 0$
- $P_{G_{2,1}}(t) = load_2(t)$ and $P_{G_{2,2}}(t) = 0$

With the same reasoning, the solution of the simplified optimization problem is:

- $P_{G_1}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t)$ and $P_{G_2}(t) = 0$

The solutions of the two optimization problems are the same.

If $load_1(t) \geq P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \geq P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$:

(MO-1) becomes $P_{G_{1,2}}(t) \leq load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$. With (LB-1), we obtain:

- $P_{G_{1,1}}(t) = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_{1,2}}(t) = load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$

This is the same for DHN 2:

- $P_{G_{2,1}}(t) = P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_{2,2}}(t) = load_2(t) - P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$

With the same reasoning, the solution of the simplified optimization problem is:

- $P_{G_1}(t) = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_2}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} - P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$

The solutions of the two optimization problems are the same.

If $load_1(t) \geq P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \leq P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}$:

For the full optimization problem, solutions are (same reasoning as precedent cases):

- $P_{G_{1,1}}(t) = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_{1,2}}(t) = load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$
- $P_{G_{2,1}}(t) = load_2(t)$ and $P_{G_{2,2}}(t) = 0$

For the simplified case, constraint (AGG) is activated and becomes:

$$\overline{P_{G_1}}(t) = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + load_2(t)$$

On the other hand, (MO) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{G_2}(t) &\leq \max(load(t) - \overline{P_{G_1}}(t); 0) \\ &\leq \max(load_1(t) + load_2(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} - load_2(t); 0) \\ &\leq load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} \end{aligned}$$

With these two ceilings and the (LB) constraint, only one solution remains admissible:

- $P_{G_1}(t) = P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + load_2(t)$
- $P_{G_2}(t) = load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$

1.5 Remark on merit order assumptions

We demonstrated that for the aggregation of two DHNs with two plants, at time t when plant $G_{i,1}$ has a marginal cost inferior to plant $G_{i,2}$, it is sufficient to add the following constraint to have the same optimization problems:

$$\overline{P_{G_1}}(t) = \min \left(P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}; load_1(t) \right) + \min \left(P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}; load_2(t) \right) \quad (\text{AGG})$$

Now let us consider an instant t^* when $G_{i,2}$ has a marginal cost inferior to $G_{i,1}$. First, the constraint (AGG) still limit the production of G_1 . But this limit is useless as G_2 is used in priority. Indeed, the load seen by G_1 is $load_1(t) + load_2(t) - P_{G_{1,2}}^{max} - P_{G_{2,2}}^{max}$, which is always inferior to $\min \left(P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}; load_1(t) \right) + \min \left(P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}; load_2(t) \right)$ (because $load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,2}}^{max} \leq P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}$ due to (LB-1)).

We add the constraint on the production of G_2 :

$$\overline{P_{G_2}}(t) = \min \left(P_{G_{1,2}}^{max}; load_1(t) \right) + \min \left(P_{G_{2,2}}^{max}; load_2(t) \right) \quad (\text{AGG-2})$$

This constraint is sufficient to ensure that optimization problems are equivalent at time t^* , with the same demonstration as in Section 1.4.

1.6 Remark on redundancy

Here, we constrained the base plant G_1 , but we could also have constrained the peak plant G_2 equivalently with the constraint:

$$P_{G_2}(t) \geq \min \left(load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max}; 0 \right) + \min \left(load_2(t) - P_{G_{2,1}}^{max}; 0 \right) \quad (\text{AGG-min})$$

The two first subcases do not need additional constraints. In the third subcase, (AGG-min) becomes:

$$P_{G_2}(t) \geq load_1(t) - P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + 0$$

On the other hand, we have (LB):

$$P_{G_1}(t) + P_{G_2}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t)$$

Injecting (LB) into (AGG-min):

$$\begin{aligned} load_2(t) - P_{G_1}(t) &\geq -P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \\ P_{G_1}(t) &\leq P_{G_{1,1}}^{max} + load_2(t) \end{aligned}$$

This is the same constraint as (AGG), then the constraints (AGG) and (AGG-min) are equivalent in this case.

2 Recurrence: 2 DHNs with n plants

Figure 2: Aggregation of two DHNs into an aggregated one

Let us show, by recurrence, that this result remains true for two DHNs with n plants. We suppose, without losing generality, that the n plants are ordered by merit order: the first one has the lowest marginal cost, the second one the second lowest marginal, etc. It implies that the n -th plant is always the most expensive.

Recurrence property on $n \in \mathbb{N}$: "The solution of the simplified problem with added constraints is the same as the full problem"

Initialisation: Precedent case

Recurrence step: Suppose that the property is verified for $n - 1$ plants. Let us study the case with n plants. The optimization problem is:

$$\min \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \text{cost}_{G_{i,j}} \right) \quad (\text{OBJ-i})$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n P_{G_{i,j}}(t) = \text{load}_i(t) \quad (\text{LB-i})$$

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 2; n \rrbracket, P_{G_{i,k}}(t) \leq \max \left(\text{load}_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \overline{P_{G_{i,j}}}(t); 0 \right) \quad (\text{MO-i-k})$$

Simplified optimization problem:

$$\min \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \text{cost}_{G_j} \right) \quad (\text{OBJ-G})$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n P_{G_j}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t) \quad (\text{LB})$$

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 2; n \rrbracket, P_{G_k}(t) \leq \max \left(load_1(t) + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \overline{P_{G_j}}(t); 0 \right) \quad (\text{MO-k})$$

Added constraints :

$$\begin{aligned} \forall k \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, \\ \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) \leq \min \left(load_1(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} \right) + \\ \min \left(load_2(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{2,j}}^{max} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{AGG-k})$$

If $load_1(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}(t)$:

The merit order constraints imply that:

- $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{1,j}}(t) = P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_{1,n}}(t) = load_1(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$
- $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{2,j}}(t) = P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_{2,n}}(t) = load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$
- $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_j}(t) = P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$ and $P_{G_n}(t) = load_1(t) + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$

Hence, the solutions of the two optimization problems are the same.

Else if $load_1(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}(t)$:

The n-th merit order constraint implies that $P_{G_n}(t) \leq 0$. Hence the problems are equivalent to the problems with only (n-1) plants. We use the recurrence property.

Else $load_1(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}(t)$:

For the full optimization problem, the solutions were already computed in precedented sub-cases:

- $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{1,j}}(t) = P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$, and $P_{G_{1,n}}(t) = load_1(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$
- $\exists l \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, \forall j \in \llbracket 1; l-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{2,j}}(t) = P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}, P_{G_{2,l}}(t) = load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$, and $\forall j \in \llbracket l+1; n \rrbracket, P_{G_{2,j}}(t) = 0$

Let us study the simplified optimization problem. Let $l \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket$ be such that:

- $load_2(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$ and $load_2(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$

$\forall k \in \llbracket 1; l-1 \rrbracket$, (AGG-k) becomes:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$$

As all plants are arranged by ascending merit order, all plants indexed inferior to l produce at their maximum power:

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 1; l-1 \rrbracket, P_{G_k}(t) = P_{G_{1,k}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,k}}^{max}$$

For $k = l$, (AGG-k) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_j}(t) + P_{G_l}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}) + P_{G_l}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
P_{G_l}(t) &\leq P_{G_{1,l}}^{max} + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

Due to the merit order, $P_{G_l}(t) = P_{G_{1,l}}^{max} + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}$.

$\forall k \in \llbracket l+1; n-1 \rrbracket$, (AGG-k) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_j}(t) + P_{G_l}(t) + \sum_{j=l+1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}) + P_{G_{1,l}}^{max} + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=l+1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + load_2(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^l P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=l+1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=l+1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=l+1}^k P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

By a finite recurrence on $j \in \llbracket l+1; n-1 \rrbracket$, we easily show that $P_{G_j}(t) = P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$ thanks to the previous constraint and the merit order assumption.

If $k = n$, (AGG-k) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{j=1}^n P_{G_j}(t) \leq load_1(t) + load_2(t) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_j}(t) + P_{G_l}(t) + \sum_{j=l+1}^{n-1} P_{G_j}(t) + P_{G_n}(t) \leq load_1(t) + load_2(t) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}) + P_{G_l}(t) + \sum_{j=l+1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_n}(t) \leq load_1(t) + load_2(t) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} (P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_{2,j}}^{max}) + P_{G_{1,l}}^{max} + load_2(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{2,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=l+1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_n}(t) \leq load_1(t) + load_2(t) \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max} + P_{G_n}(t) \leq load_1(t)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $P_{G_n}(t) = load_1(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{1,j}}^{max}$.

Combining all these results, we proved that the two optimization problems have the same solutions.

3 Recurrence: p DHNs with n plants

Figure 3: Aggregation of p DHNs with n plants into an aggregated one

3.1 Notations and assumptions

Let DHN be the set containing all the DHNs: $Card(DHN) = p \in \mathbb{N}$

Simplified optimization problem:

$$\min \left(\sum_{j=1}^n cost_{G_j} \right) \quad (\text{OBJ-G})$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n P_{G_j}(t) = load(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p load_i(t) \quad (\text{LB})$$

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 2; n \rrbracket, P_{G_k}(t) \leq \max \left(\sum_{i=1}^p load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \overline{P_{G_j}}(t); 0 \right) \quad (\text{MO-k})$$

Added constraints:

$$\forall k \in \llbracket 1; n-1 \rrbracket, \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) \leq \sum_{i=1}^p \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \quad (\text{AGG-k})$$

3.2 Demonstration

Recurrence property on $n \in \mathbb{N}$: "The solution of the simplified optimization problem with added constraints is the same as the full problem".

Initialisation:

For $n = 1$, the two problems are identical.

Recurrence step:

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we assume the recurrence property is true for $n - 1$.

If $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, load_i(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$:

The solution of the full problem is:

- $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, \forall j \in \llbracket 1; n - 1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{i,j}}(t) = P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$
- $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, P_{G_{i,n}}(t) = load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$

The solution of the simplified problem is:

- $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; n - 1 \rrbracket, P_{G_j}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$
- $P_{G_n}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right)$

Then, the two solutions are the same in this subcase.

Else if: $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, load_i(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$:

In this case $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, P_{G_{i,n}}(t) = 0$ and $P_{G_n}(t) = 0$. Then, we are in the $(n - 1)$ case and use the recurrence property.

Else: $\exists i_1, i_2 \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, load_{i_1}(t) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i_1,j}}^{max}$ and $load_{i_2}(t) \geq \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i_2,j}}^{max}$

$\forall k \in \llbracket 1; n - 1 \rrbracket$, let us define the set $E_k = \{i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket, load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \geq 0 \text{ and } load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \leq 0\}$. This set gathers the DHNs i in which all the generators $G_{i,j}$ with $j \in \llbracket 1; k \rrbracket$ are sufficient and necessary to meet $load_i$.

Let us take k_{min} such as $\forall k < k_{min}, E_k = \emptyset$ and k_{max} such as $\forall k > k_{max}, E_k = \emptyset$.

For all $k \in \llbracket 1; k_{min} - 1 \rrbracket$: This is the same reasoning as subcase 1:

- $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \quad \forall k \in \llbracket 1; k_{min} - 1 \rrbracket, P_{G_{i,k}}(t) = P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$
- $\forall k \in \llbracket 1; k_{min} - 1 \rrbracket, P_{G_k}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$

For all $k \in \llbracket k_{min}; k_{max} \rrbracket$: For the full optimization problem, we have:

- $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k} E_p \quad P_{G_{i,k}} = P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$
- $\forall i \in \cup_{p \leq k-1} E_p, P_{G_{i,k}} = 0$
- $\forall i \in E_k, P_{G_{i,k}} = load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$

We will now demonstrate, by strong finite recurrence on $k \in \llbracket k_{min}; k_{max} \rrbracket$ that:

$$P_{G_k}(t) = \sum_{i \in E_k} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} \quad (\text{Recurrence}_k)$$

Initialisation:

(AGG-k) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}} P_{G_j}(t) &\leq \sum_{i=1}^p \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
\sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_j}(t) + P_{G_{k_{min}}}(t) &\leq \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus E_{k_{min}}} \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} load_i(t) \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
P_{G_{k_{min}}}(t) &\leq \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus E_{k_{min}}} \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_j}(t)
\end{aligned}$$

As $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; k_{min} - 1 \rrbracket$, $P_{G_j}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{G_{k_{min}}}(t) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus E_{k_{min}}} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
P_{G_{k_{min}}}(t) &\leq \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus E_{k_{min}}} P_{G_{i,k_{min}}}^{max} + \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
&\Leftrightarrow \\
P_{G_{k_{min}}}(t) &\leq \sum_{i \in E_{k_{min}}} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus E_{k_{min}}} P_{G_{i,k_{min}}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

Recurrence step:

Let $k \in \llbracket k_{min}; k_{max} \rrbracket$.

(AGG-k) is:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) \leq \sum_{i=1}^p \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right)$$

Let us study the first member:

$$\sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_j}(t) + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} P_{G_l}(t) + P_{G_k}(t)$$

As $\forall j \in \llbracket 1; k_{min} - 1 \rrbracket$, $P_{G_j}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_j}(t) &= \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i=1}^p P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
\sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} P_{G_j}(t) &= \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

And, with the recurrence property,

$$\forall l \in \llbracket k_{min}; k - 1 \rrbracket, P_{G_l}(t) = \sum_{i \in E_l} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max}$$

Therefore, summing this last expression on $l \in \llbracket k_{min}; k-1 \rrbracket$:

$$\sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} P_{G_l}(t) = \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \left(\sum_{i \in E_l} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} \right)$$

Combining the two new expressions, the first member becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &= \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \\ &\quad \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \left(\sum_{i \in E_l} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} \right) + P_{G_k}(t) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} + \\ &\quad \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} load_i(t) + P_{G_k}(t) \end{aligned}$$

As $\cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p = (\cup_{p \leq l} E_p) \cup (\cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p)$, then $\llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p = (\llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p) \cup (\cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p)$ because $\cup_{p \leq l} E_p$ and $\cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p$ are disjoint.

Then :

$$\sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq l} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} = \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max}$$

The first member then becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_j}(t) &= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,l}}^{max} + \\ &\quad \sum_{j=1}^{k_{min}-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} load_i(t) + P_{G_k}(t) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{l < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \\ &\quad - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} load_i(t) + P_{G_k}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Let us decompose the second member:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^p \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) &= \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} \min \left(load_i(t); \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^k \sum_{i \in E_l} load_i(t) - \sum_{i \in E_k} \sum_{j=1}^k P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\ &= \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} + \sum_{l=k_{min}}^k \sum_{i \in E_l} load_i(t) - \\ &\quad \sum_{i \in E_k} \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{i \in E_k} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} \end{aligned}$$

Putting the two members together and simplifying the most obvious terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{i < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + P_{G_k}(t) \leq \\
& \sum_{i \in E_k} load_i(t) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} - \sum_{i \in E_k} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{i \in E_k} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{i < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + P_{G_k}(t) \leq \\
& \sum_{i \in E_k} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} - \sum_{i \in E_k} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max} \\
& \Leftrightarrow \\
& \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{i < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} + P_{G_k}(t) \leq \\
& \sum_{i \in E_k} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1;p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

Let us show that $\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in \cup_{i < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} = \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$.

On the one hand, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in \cup_{i < p \leq (k-1)} E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{p=i+1}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
& = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \left(\sum_{p=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{p=1}^i \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \\
& = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \left(\sum_{p=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^i \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \\
& = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{p=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l=k_{min}}^i \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
& = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{p=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{i=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{l=k_{min}}^i \sum_{l \in E_p} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} &= \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{j=l}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) \\
&= \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} \sum_{j=l}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{j=l}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{i \in E_l} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} - \sum_{j=k_{min}}^{k-1} \sum_{l=k_{min}}^j \sum_{i \in E_l} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, due to the merit order, we obtain the recurrence property:

$$P_{G_k}(t) = \sum_{i \in E_k} \left(load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max} \right) + \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$$

For all $k \in \llbracket k_{max} + 1; n \rrbracket$: For the full optimization problem, we have:

- $\forall k \in \llbracket k_{max}; n - 1 \rrbracket \quad \forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k_{max}} E_p \quad P_{G_{i,k}} = P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$
- $\forall i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k_{max}} E_p \quad P_{G_{i,n}} = load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_{i,j}}^{max}$
- $\forall k \in \llbracket k_{max}; n \rrbracket \quad \forall i \in \cup_{p \leq k_{max}} E_p \quad P_{G_{i,k}} = 0$

For the simplified optimization problem:

- $\forall k \in \llbracket k_{max}; n - 1 \rrbracket \quad P_{G_k}(t) = \sum_{i \in \llbracket 1; p \rrbracket \setminus \cup_{p \leq k_{max}} E_p} P_{G_{i,k}}^{max}$
- $P_{G_n}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^p load_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} P_{G_j}(t)$

Conclusion of the subcase We showed for all $k \in \llbracket 1; n \rrbracket$ that the solutions of the two problems were equivalent.

Conclusion

We proved that for all $n, p \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$, optimizing the functioning of p DHNs with n plants is equivalent to optimizing one DHN with n plants.